

On Design and the C-A-B Paradigm

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Abstract

Contemporary thinking in the field of design views *designing* as a *possibility-creating activity* focused on the *relationship* between the user and the design and the subsequent desired *experience* that is created. Designing *contexts for experience* instead of products, objects and/or environments individuals' senses are evoked and engaged and emotional reactions are formed. This person-design interactive experience is immediate, personal, un-buffered and primarily affective involving a great variety of emotions. While this proposition is not without appeal it might also be incomplete. The following theoretical discussion strives to better understand *how* design creates a context for experience probing the notion of 'experience' and the implications that understanding 'experience' might have to effective design.

1. Introduction:

The claim made by contemporary thinking in the field of design is that *designing* has to be viewed as a *possibility-creating activity* focused on the *relationship* between the user and the design (be it designed products, objects or environments) and the subsequent desired *experience* that is created (Hekkert, 2001). According to this view design shifts from creating products to creating *contexts for experience* where the user is seduced to experience the designed object or reality with all his or her senses (Overbeeke et al., 1999). By designing *contexts for experience* instead of products, objects and/or environments individual subjective interaction with the design shifts attention from ‘results of interaction’ towards ‘involvement during interaction’ (Hummels, 1999) where the senses are evoked and engaged and emotional reactions are formed. This person-design interactive experience is immediate, personal, un-buffered and primarily affective involving a great variety of emotions.

In a successful industrial design object, the sensory, the functional, the emotional are engaged simultaneously and here we have another kind of metaphor. Just as is in a successful painting, your subject matter and your style become unified, play off against each other as counter points and rhythms. In a successful industrial design object, function disappears into form. It’s echoed in it, resonates with it. The object can be manipulated into material level. You can take it, you can use it. You can open the bottle, you can open the door. You can do whatever you need with the tool. This is the way you engage with the consumer and develop a bond with the consumer and the product. When you have a successful industrial design object, it’s something that you can use, it’s user friendly. But the person sees it, or the person feels it. The feeling, the seeing, the sensing of the texture, they are what it’s about, they are what the tool is. I’m arguing that when those two are together, you have again a metaphor. People spontaneously feel the metaphor. They don’t think about it—whether I like this two or not—they know. It’s not an object of reflection. Why? Because intellectual feelings are combined. Because function and form are combined (Cupchik, 2003)

While this proposition is not without intuitive appeal it might also be incomplete. The following discussion raises and addresses questions about the very basic assumptions made by this proposition starting with *how* design creates a context for experience and moving to probe the notion of ‘experience’ and the implications that understanding ‘experience’ might have to effective design.

2. How design creates a context for experience?

Introducing the C-A-B paradigm social scientists and researchers (primarily in the fields of psychology, marketing and branding) attempted to demonstrate how behavior is impacted and experiences are generated. Within the framework of the C-A-B paradigm (Cognition – Emotion – Behavior) experience evolves out of cognition (C) that determines affect (A) which in turn results in behavior (B). Holbrook & Batra (1987) provide an excellent review of the C-A-B paradigm research and point to the usefulness of emotions as mediators between cognitions and behaviors. Following this line of thought, design decisions, including ‘brand design’, ‘product design’ or ‘workplace design’ decisions, are able to elicit and sustain a desired experience; the bonding of consumers and brands, satisfaction with a product, or productivity at work respectively, mainly because they trigger the ‘right’ cognitions, that in turn give rise to the ‘right’ emotions¹.

Researchers like Edell and Burke (1987) and Woods (2004) suggest that branding for example involves triggering and consequently engaging consumers’ emotions through brand messages to ultimately gain a ‘share of heart’ (Day, 1989). Wansink (2003) further advances our understanding of how such bond, or experience of relating to a brand, evolves. This researcher discusses a means-end theory adopting Aaker’s (1996) hierarchical order of consumer product knowledge and perception, which ranges from product *attributes* to consumption patterns (*consequences*) and further to personal *values* as shown in Figure 1 below:

¹ "... in the action mode, feelings are the shadows of cognition. When the pattern of ideas is coherent, then there is a feeling of calm or pleasure. When the ideas do not fit together harmoniously, there is the experience of tension. In a sense, feelings are almost mechanically (i.e., isomorphically) related to changes in the content of cognition." (Cupchik, 2004)

Figure 1: Illustration of a Hierarchical Value Map

To demonstrate this hierarchical relationship Wansink uses the example of a convertible sports car. This car leads to feelings of excitement and youth that in turn support one or more of the consumer’s values. While product attributes describe the technical properties of that product, consequences and values, are often related to deep emotional needs that represent the real reason why a certain brand is attractive to consumers.

Following the C-A-B paradigm’s line of thought if design is experienced cognitively, then impacting behaviors is mitigated by emotions (C -> A -> B) which are likely to emerge and yet over which we have only limited control². However if design is experienced emotionally we are only one step removed from impacting behavior (A ->

² “What is the role that emotion should play in our approaches to design? “How do we design for emotion?” Good question, but it implies that one can identify emotion as a design target, then craft an artifact (an application, a device, a thing, for example) that meets this target” Don Norman, Symposium on Foundations of Interaction Design, 2003

B), an opportunity of interest to many product, brand and environment designers³ (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Proposed Design-Emotion Relationship Within the C-A-B Framework

Several key questions arise, all relevant to better understand how design creates a context for experience, including: What are the ways by which we can impact emotions to generate experience and how are they different from means by which we design to impact cognitions that in turn generate emotions that supposedly trigger behaviors? Is one expected to utilize different design levers when going after impacting emotions as oppose to impacting cognitions? It is also important to challenge the anticipated impact's universality by asking if design is expected to affect all individuals similarly with no regard to individual preferences and contextual factors? But making use of the C-A-B paradigm in explaining how design creates a context for desired experiences necessitates first and foremost that we address the viability of the C-A-B framework in explaining experience generation altogether. While this line of research proposes an order of

³ Mahajan and Wind caution "if you're not using emotions to position your products and services – any product or service – you're missing a tremendous opportunity...It is affective, rather than cognitive, story of and about your offerings that will win customers' hearts (and minds), and this is what companies need to create, manage and harvest - emotional brand loyalty" (Mahajan & Wind, 2002 p.38 and 41).

cognition, affect and behavior, it also presupposes that such order is kept as linear, that it can be activated by impacting the first link in the chain (cognition), and that much of this process of cognitions impacting emotions which in turn impact behaviors occurs in the conscious world. Are these all viable propositions? Let us elaborate.

3. Taking a deeper dive: Probing questions about design, experience, emotions and possible interactions

When thinking of ‘contexts for experience’ certain questions arise. Is ‘experiencing’ a mental state; a physical state; an activity? Are people aware of their experiences? Why are some experiences remembered while others are forgotten? Why do people experience a similar stimulus or event differently? Finally, why do some stimuli inspire activity and engagement while others leave individuals unmoved and disinterested? The claim that design can create a context for desired experience doesn’t necessarily address these questions. Instead of attending to the complexity of the ‘experiences’ and ‘positive emotions’ phenomena the literature focuses on identifying design’s impact. While the latter is clearly an important pursuit in itself, following this inquiry path is likely to leave us only partially knowledgeable. To better understand the claim that design can create a context for desired experience, theories of experience and emotions and the possible relationship between them need to be further analyzed.

What is ‘*experience*’? The Merriam-Webster e-dictionary provides various definitions for the term ‘experience’ emphasizing the direct *observation of* or *participation in* events⁴. Interestingly, these definitions do not specify whether ‘experience’ is an *emotional engagement* or a *cognitive perception*. Philosophers and psychologists have long attempted to formulate an agreed upon theory of experience with only limited success. In the absence of one governing perspective, one’s perspective on what ‘experience’ really is, is largely dependent on the view they adopted. For example,

⁴ Definitions include: **1 a** : direct observation of or participation in events as a basis of knowledge **b** : the fact or state of having been affected by or gained knowledge through direct observation or participation; **2 a** : practical knowledge, skill, or practice derived from direct observation of or participation in events or in a particular activity **b** : the length of such participation <has 10 years *experience* in the job>; **3 a** : the conscious events that make up an individual life **b** : the events that make up the conscious past of a community or nation or mankind generally; **4** : something personally encountered, undergone, or lived through; **5** : the act or process of directly perceiving events or reality

‘experience’ would be regarded as ‘participating in events’ if one thinks phenomenologically⁵ (Husserl., 1989; Merleau-Ponty, 1996; Sartre, 1964; Chalmers, 2002). Experience might also be the ‘observation of events’ if one has a naturalistic perspective⁶ (Devitt, 1998; Miller, 1987). Both approaches, despite their apparently different orientations presuppose consciousness, a subject heavily investigated in recent years (see the work of Rosenthal, 1986; Dretske, 1993; Block, 1995; Lycan, 1996).

Reserachers distinguish *mental-state* consciousness from *access* consciousness. *Mental-state* consciousness is *like something [to experince]*, which is likely to be felt (Nagel, 1974) while *access consciousness* centers on thoughts or judgments (Block, 1995) which are primarily cognitive. Some theorists believe that these states of consciousness are independent and do not co-occur. Still others doubt whether mental states can be phenomenally-conscious (experienced and felt) without also being conscious in the functionally-definable sense (perceived). Even greater dispute ensues over whether phenomenal consciousness can be *reductively explained* in functional and/or representational terms (i.e. that expeirences and feelings be explained through cognitions).

Cognitive (or *representational*) theories maintain that this is possible. Such theories assume that phenomenal consciousness (*mental-state* consciousness) consists of a kind of intentional or representational content. Accordingly, a phenomenally-conscious percept of the color Red, for example, carries with it analog content *red* which is constructed in such a way that it can present thoughts about red, or trigger one into actions which are in one way or another guided by ‘redness’. Yet opposing views argue that phenomenal consciousness is indescribable because the content of associations can easily slip through the mesh of any conceptual net. A person can always distinguish many more shades of

⁵ The discipline of phenomenology can be defined as the study of structures of experience, or consciousness. By definition, phenomenology is the study of ‘phenomena’: appearances of things, or things as they appear in our experience, or the ways we experience things, thus the meanings things have in our experience. This field of philosophy studies conscious experience as experienced from the subjective point of view.

⁶ Naturalized epistemology treats knowledge as a natural phenomenon, objective and susceptible of investigation by empirical science methods. It takes for granted the existence of knowledge and knowledge as independent of individual perception and/or awareness. Naturalized epistemologists do not concern themselves with what counts as ‘knowledge’ properly speaking.

red than they have concepts for, or could describe in language. According to this view phenomenal consciousness while experienced and requires awareness is not necessarily reducible to words and cognitions, or else explained through functional terms.

While both states presuppose that experience requires awareness one has to ask if all states of experience are indeed conscious? Some theories of consciousness believe that most mental states are comprised of both conscious and non-conscious qualities. Accordingly these theorists argue that beliefs, values and desires can be activated non-consciously. (i.e., new problem-solving approach that emerges during sleep, or a person's attention that is directed to other tasks). What makes a conscious and a non-conscious mental state different is awareness of course. Conscious states are *states of which the subject is aware*, states which are either based on perception or experience, or a belief or thought. However when one is unaware, can they still perceive and be impacted by their perception? Can there be for example such a thing as a non-conscious visual perceptual state? Armstrong (1968) uses the example of absent-minded driving to demonstrate that while a person may not be aware of the route he has recently taken, nor of any of the obstacles he managed to avoid on the way, he must surely have been *seeing* both the road and the obstacles while driving to his destination.

Along the line of Armstrong's argument, Milner and Goodale (1995) provide a review of a variety of neurological and neuro-psychological evidence for the independence of two distinct visual systems, one specializing in the 'on-line' visual control of action while the other is responsible for 'off-line' functions such as visual learning and object recognition. Only the experiences relevant to the on-line action-control system are phenomenally-conscious. These researchers make a powerful case for distinguishing between conscious and non-conscious visual percepts suggesting that some experiences perceived by the visual system might generate impact while 'flying under the awareness screen'. But what implications does this discussion have to our understanding of 'experience'.

Given that experience can be subjective or objective, emotional or conceptual, aware or unconscious depending on the school of thought to which one ascribes, why is it assumed

that experiencing a designed context registers with individuals, and triggers desired emotions rather than negative cognitions for example?

Theories on emotions do not help in addressing this question. Not only are there multiple theories and constructs attempting to define what emotions are, but these accounts offer an heterogeneous and somewhat confusing amalgamation of ideas⁷. While many theorists in this area converge on a dimensional view that argues for emotions as positive-negative and/or primary-secondary (Plutchik, 2001), only few address the nature of emotions as implicit or explicit cognitions or constructs (Clore et al, 2005). Furthermore, emotion literature does not speak in one voice on the question of context (i.e. are emotions universal or contextual in both appearance and meanings), nor does it bring clarity to questions about the impact of emotions on behavior although such effect is implicitly assumed⁸.

When it comes to psychologists commenting on emotion-cognition relationships, the literature is inconclusive whereby some argue for separation of the two while others see them as closely interlinked.⁹ Lastly, emotion literature is also split on the issue of consciousness of emotions. Conscious feelings have traditionally been viewed as a central and necessary ingredient of emotion. For example Frijda (1999) sees emotions as the experience of pleasure and pain while Clore (1994) wrote about “Why Emotions Are Never Unconscious” succinctly summarizing his view on the matter. Recently however researchers have begun to argue that emotions can be genuinely unconscious (Winkielman & Berridge, 2004) by demonstrating that positive and negative reactions can be elicited subliminally and remain inaccessible to introspection. This notion is

⁷ More than 90 definitions have been offered over the past century, and there are almost as many theories of emotion – not to mention a complex array of overlapping words in our languages to describe them. Plutchik, 2001; <http://www.americanscientist.org/july-august2001>.

⁸ For example, Desmet (2004) offer that triggering a mix of positive and negative emotions might be of greater influence as it generates tension that also creates attention and traction. Thus proposing that design can act as a context for generating a desired experience requires further specification of what is regarded as desired emotions [that might not be only positive emotions]

⁹ “...one of the great pitfalls in western philosophy in the last 300 years has been to separate intellect from emotion. The separation of intellect from emotion is wrong. There is no emotion without cognition and vice versa. There’s no cognition without emotion. Thought and feelings go hand in hand in an intimate way” (Cupchik, 2003)

consistent with evolutionary considerations suggesting that systems underlying basic affective reactions originated prior to systems for conscious awareness.

Similar to various streams of philosophy, emotion literature is somewhat indecisive and inconclusive. Emotions can be conscious or unconscious, positive or negative, individual or universal, depending on the view adopted. Hence, experiencing a context generated by design might trigger any or none of the above responses. It might generate unconscious-negative emotions or alternatively conscious and positive ones, or else, it might not generate any desired emotional context whatsoever.

The meaning of ‘experience’ is not at all trivial and simple to understand and agreed on. So far, the two prominent distinctions between the various views are: (a) Experience as affective or cognitive, and (b) experience as conscious or unconscious (See table 1 below).

	Cognition	Affect
Unconscious	Armstrong (1968)	Winkielman & Berridge (2004)
Conscious	(Block, 1995)	Frijda (1999) Clore (1994)

Table 1: Multiple Orientations towards ‘Experience’

While both experience and emotions as hard-to-define constructs are held loose, conceptualizing design as a trigger of emotional experience might be a rushed

proposition. Research on design as context for emotional experience should build both the empirical evidence as well as the conceptual clarity for these constructs and their possible relationships.

4. Where do we go from here?

Our discussion probed the meaning of "designing experience". Some argue that it is an act of choreography of meanings in the others' mind but how is it different from, for example, making a movie? In the case of linear narratives, such as film and music, the experience is predetermined by the maker and is framed for and 'imposed' on the viewer/listener. However, in the case of a functional object, such as a product, a prescribed event does not reveal itself until the user interacts with it. Therefore, the design must solicit the user's desired action, which triggers the product's functionality/experience. The user's experience is an inseparable element of the designed system. Such understanding is at the heart of Hekkert's claim for design as a generator of contexts for experience (2001).

This shift towards viewing *designing* as a *possibility-creating activity* that focuses on the *relationship* between the user and the design and moves away from the result of interaction into involvement *in and during* interaction (Hummels, 1999) implies a *conscious and active user engagement*. Csikszentmihalyi (1990, 1993) who studied *flow* as a qualitative compound of experiences points to how the actor is in complete involvement with the activity. Such state of experience presupposes that: action and awareness are merged, control is imposed on actions and environment, goals for engaging in the experience are clear and the feedback and affect generated through the experience is positive (Novak et al, 1997, 1998). Cupchik comment:

...we experience *distinctive function* when the flow of experience is speeded up and we can feel the fluidity of engaged responses. But we experience *distinctive form* when the flow of experience is slowed down so that we notice the structure of salient sensory properties related to line, texture, colour, and so on. (Cupchik, 2005)

Design literature reviewed here makes two key implicit presuppositions. First it assumes consciousness of those who participate in experiencing the design and second it assumes

control of the designer as the instigator and director of the flow, the activity, the user's experience. While such view is empowering and engaging for designers who are presented with the challenge of creating contexts rather than products or brands, it fails to acknowledge unconsciousness emotions and cognitions, argued for by other theorists. How do we account for such experiences that are generated 'bottom up' rather than 'top down'¹⁰? Clearly these experiences are directed by the user rather than the designer. They are individualized and may form 'out of context' vis-à-vis the design intention (Figure 3 below).

Figure 3: A dialectic relationship between design and experience

Take for example the times when we are immersed in a flow while not being aware of our participation (see the example of driving absent-mindedly). This experience is emergent if only because it is not guided consciously. Other times we do not get engaged at all even when design messages are clearly directed at us and invite us to participate and experience. Here the design intent is not efficacious enough to generate experience

¹⁰ Top-down design decisions relate to how one understands a problem or a need and designs to satisfy requirements and impact experience. 'Bottom-up' on the other hand relates to spontaneous experience, one that emerges rather than directed.

beyond introducing features and attributes. People are not always conscious actors that are ‘hooked’ through their cognitions as action theories (Cupchik, 2004) would like to assume.

There are complementary traditions in the psychological study of emotions, which contrast action with experience. The action tradition...[provides] an “objective” analysis of emotion, but the experience tradition, which encompasses psychodynamics and phenomenology, addresses its ‘subjective’ aspects. The action approach...can be expressed in the simple formula, Emotion = Arousal + Cognition, whereby the body serves as a source of energy for executing plans and realizing goals...The experience approach...define[s] emotion as ... uniquely patterned for the different primary affects, such [as] happiness, sadness, fear, and anger...Designing for the action mode is a top-down process whereby a tool or instrument facilitates the realizing of goals. It embodies clear cognitive plans and must engage arousal in such a way as to energize the process and sustain attention... Designing for the experience mode requires that the design object, whether a tool or an image of some kind, be placed in a broader social context. (Cupchik, 2004)

Claiming that design creates a context for experience is important but insufficient in explaining the various states of user awareness and the emergent nature of experience. Future research could address the contingency of designing for unconscious affect versus conscious cognitions. While in both cases the resultant behavior might be the same, it is still intuitively appealing to assume that context and design levers might matter in their ability to unleash users’ desired experiences (See table 2).

	Cognition	Affect
Unconscious	Context? Design Lever?	Context? Design Lever?
Conscious	Context? Design Lever?	Context? Design Lever?

Table 2: Acknowledging contingency relationship between mental state, experience, context and design lever

Advertisers often times design their messages to circumvent the memory-building processes (from sensual to short term and to long term memory, Cowan, 2000). and ‘insert’ a desired meaning right into the long-term memory hub of associations without eliciting rejection of the idea. In this example bypassing conscious cognition and emotion allow for effective management of meaning and experiences. Interior designers often inject a particular color into the space intuiting that such color selection will trigger a desired behavior (see for example the work of Birren on color in hospitals, 1978). Here the use of color attempts to trigger unconscious affect supportive of the healing experience the designer is interested at. It might be possible for design to leverage unconscious cognitions and affect just as much that it is interested in creating contexts for experience that presuppose user consciousness. The question of user awareness and its importance to the design’s efficacy in creating context for desired experience is yet to be understood.

While the shift towards generating experience seems exciting and promising, future research should formulate ideas and evidence to support a contingency view of design as a generator of contexts for experience. Studies can address questions about the role of awareness, the universality of design’s impact, the different efficiencies associated with attracting cognitions versus engaging emotions and the simultaneous management of top-down-bottom-up reality creating processes by design.

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